

PURPOSE, TASKS AND SOCIAL PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Rozimbayeva Maftuna

Andijan State Pedagogical Institute,
Pre-school education, 1st level student.

Abstract: This article reflects the purpose, tasks and social pedagogical possibilities of inclusive education. Inclusive education is a model that seeks to meet the educational needs of children, youth and adults, and reflects processes such as paying special attention to those who are prone to marginalization and social exclusion.

Key words: Inclusive education, pedagogical technologies, laws, disabled, pedagogical-psychological, disability, adaptation to social life.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of all the reforms carried out in our republic is to build a solid foundation for the future of our country. This foundation is created as a result of raising healthy, mature and well-rounded individuals. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan guarantees the right to education for all. Our national legislation also stipulates equal rights for people with disabilities in realizing their potential. Today, a number of works are being carried out in our country to create truly inclusive conditions for children with developmental disabilities so that they can get quality education and later find a decent job.

Conducting correctional educational, educational and developmental work with children with limited opportunities, adapting them to social society, bringing them to adulthood so that they can serve themselves and benefit the society to a certain extent are among the most urgent issues of every country. is one. After all, according to the words of our president Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, "The spirituality of

any nation is determined by its attention to disabled people living in this society."

UNICEF, a children's organization that supports the education of children with disabilities around the world, did not ignore the inclusive education module. UNICEF deals with the issues of inclusion of inclusive education in the education system of Uzbekistan. The task of inclusive education is to provide quality education to all children, regardless of their abilities and status, and the principle of inclusion implies that children with disabilities should live in a family and study in a regular school together with their peers in order to have a positive, mental and social development. An inclusive education system ensures that a child in a wheelchair attends a nearby school, receives special help in learning to read and write if he/she is struggling, and a child who has dropped out is given appropriate support to return to school. Implementation of these goals has risen to the level of state policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan. As a result, international legal regulations on inclusive education, inclusive education experiences of developed foreign countries were studied, and based on them, Article 20 of the newly revised Law "On Education", "Inclusive Education" lim" and it is legal that "Inclusive education is aimed at providing equal opportunities to receive education in educational organizations for all learners, taking into account the diversity of individual educational needs and individual capabilities" reinforced with a base.

LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT ANALYSIS

Inclusive education (taken from the English language means inclusive, inclusion-to adapt, to harmonize, to include, to cover) to eliminate barriers (discrimination) between disabled and healthy children, children with special dietary needs, disabled for some reasons Education that represents inclusion in the general education process aimed at adapting adolescents to social life, regardless of developmental disabilities or economic difficulties, introduces education that is specific to all children. The main goal of inclusive education is to ensure that

children with special needs receive full education in general education institutions based on their capabilities and to create necessary conditions for every child in educational institutions. Different forms of education are organized for children with disabilities: special education, inclusive education at home, integrated education and welfare homes. Special education is integrated education organized in boarding schools, schools, home education, educational institutions specially organized for children's problems; orphanages are specially organized boarding-type education for children with severe developmental disabilities.

Ph.D., associate professor R.Shomakhmudova "Elimination of barriers between disabled and students with special needs, children with special needs and

"It is an educational system that represents the full integration of adolescents into the general education system, regardless of their developmental defects or economic difficulties, with the active participation of the family, in particular, to meet the needs of the child and adapt them to social life."

L.R.Mo'minova developed the theoretical foundations of correctional-pedagogical works to eliminate speech defects of children with disabilities of preschool age, as well as the methodology of speech therapy examination and training of children was created and implemented.

In the research work "Correction-pedagogical basis of increasing the vocabulary of mentally retarded children of preschool age" carried out by M.P. Hamidova, the methods of examining the speech of mentally retarded children were created based on general and special pedagogical research. As a result of the examination of children, the criteria of speech underdevelopment of mentally retarded children were developed. The contents and methods of correctional-pedagogical work aimed at increasing the interest in learning and speech motivation of preschool children with mental retardation by engaging their emotional-volitional spheres have been developed.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The legal and regulatory bases of inclusive education are of two types: foreign and national. Foreign foundations "Universal Declaration of Human Rights" (1948), "Convention on the Rights of the Child" (1989), "Declaration on the Rights of the Disabled" (1975), Universal Declaration "Why Education" (1990), Salamanca Declaration (1994) , relies on the Dakar Declaration (2000). The national foundations are the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan (1992), the Law on Social Protection of the Disabled (1991), the Law on Education (1997), the Law on Guarantees of Children's Rights (2008), Decree PF-5270 (2017) on measures to fundamentally improve the support system, Decree PF-5712 (2019) on the concept of development of the public education system until 2030.

Today, more than 700,000 people with disabilities live in Uzbekistan, more than 100,000 of them are under the age of 16 (according to the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic). In recent years, positive reforms have been carried out at the state level in the field of normative legal framework aimed at strengthening the rights and obligations of persons with disabilities in our republic.

Including:

1. In 2020, "On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities" was adopted, which stipulates the provision of privileges and reliefs for persons with disabilities in obtaining housing, education, providing them with work, as well as ensuring full access to existing infrastructure, information and public services. .

2. On June 7, 2021, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev signed the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Ratification of the Rights of the Disabled" No. ORQ-695 (New York, December 13, 2006), which provides for the following : The rights of persons with disabilities and the recognition that persons with disabilities have equal rights with others in all aspects of life.

Taking into account this situation, it is envisaged to take appropriate

measures to support persons with disabilities and ensure access to decision-making mechanisms, including restrictions on the mobility of disabled persons, under appropriate conditions and in accordance with legislation;

3. On October 13, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's decision No. 4860 "On measures to further improve the system of education for children with special educational needs" further improvement, personnel training, retraining and qualification improvement, as well as strengthening of the material and technical base and the provision of special devices (lifting devices, pads, fences, etc.), necessary literature, educational tools for various professions provision of equipment and educational tools is envisaged.

We can say that in recent years, effective work has been done to protect the rights of disabled people in our republic. Inclusive education also includes early access to children in need. The education of children with special needs should not end with primary and secondary special education. Vocational education and higher education of children who need special support are also required. Because one of the tasks of the inclusive education system is to fully develop children with special needs and ensure all their rights.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Inclusive education - develops the process of general education and introduces education suitable for all children. It creates comfortable conditions for the education of children by organizing additional facilities for the education of children with disabilities. Inclusive education tries to develop a methodology aimed at the education of children with different needs. Inclusive education implements the development of education that approaches the teaching of a compact type aimed at meeting different needs.

The main tasks of inclusive education are:

- Implementation of a unified state policy on the development and improvement of inclusive education in the preschool and school education

system;

- Organization and coordination of inclusive education and speech therapy centers in general secondary educational institutions.

- Inclusive education in preschools and schools, improvement of defectological services, methodical support and professional development of speech therapists, special pedagogues:

- Development of modern approaches and methods in providing socio-psychological services to children and their parents, teachers in order to create an inclusive learning environment in general education institutions;

- Making proposals for consideration by the management on state programs and other programs that provide for the further development of inclusive education, as well as mechanisms for their implementation;

- To control the creation of conditions for inclusive education in general education schools, to develop criteria for determining the quality and effectiveness of inclusive education, and to control their implementation;

- Creation of a database of general education institutions where the inclusive education system has been introduced, and the students studying in them, and its constant updating;

- Organization of psychological-pedagogical support work for teachers-speech therapists of speech therapy branches of speech therapists in inclusive conditions and development and improvement of technologies aimed at social development;

- Development and improvement of methodological support (programs, methodological recommendations for leaders, pedagogues and experts, etc.) of speech therapy branches at inclusive education and general education institutions;

- Development, improvement, trial-testing and implementation of speech therapy branches at general educational institutions, curriculum and training programs for inclusive education, taking into account advanced national and

foreign experiences, in accordance with international requirements in terms of content and quality;

- Organization and holding of conferences, training-seminars in order to develop the activity of teachers-speech therapists of speech therapy branches at inclusive education participants and general education institutions;

- To coordinate and monitor the activities of the teachers-speech therapists of the speech therapy branches established under the participants of inclusive education and general secondary education institutions, and to carry out methodical guidance.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, it can be said that inclusive education helps people with disabilities to improve their lifestyle and take their place in society. Education of children with special needs is one of the main tasks of our country. Today, our society has set itself the task of comprehensively supporting the rights of people with disabilities, implementing their opportunity to receive full education at all stages of this process. If teaching and learning in the implementation of inclusive education is somewhat effective and efficient, then not only children with disabilities, but all children will win. Inclusive education schools protect children's individual rights to education. Such an approach eliminates and reduces discrimination, because in the process of communicating with each other, children realize that they have different needs in the process of their education.

References:

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning O‘qituvchi va murabbiylar kuniga bag‘ishlangan tantanali marosimdagi nutqi. 2020-yil 30-sentabr.(<http://marifat.uz/marifat/ruknlar/rasmiy/4939.htm>)

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi qonun hujjatlari milliy bazasi. Lex.uz

M.Kasimova, S. Mo‘minova, G.Alimova, SH. Ahmedova. “Alohida ehtiyojlari bo‘lgan o‘quvchilarni psixologik qo‘llab-quvvatlash usullari” metodik

tavsiya. Toshkent 2022-yil.

Z.N.Mamarajabova, B.Q.Subanova “Inklyuziv ta’lim” o’quv qo’llanma. Toshkent-2022. 22-b.

F.U.Qodirova, D.A.Pulatova “Inkyuziv ta’lim: nazariya va amaliyot” Chirchiq – 2022. 62-bet

Qodirova N.R. “Maktabgacha ta’lim tashkilotlari faoliyatini raqamlashtirish”. “O‘ZBEKISTONDA ILM-FANNING RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI” xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjumani. Navoiy-2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7342200>

Mirzayev O. Historical and Pedagogical Roots of The Development of Entrepreneurial Culture in Uzbekistan. Spain. International Journal of Culture and Modernity 2023 ISSN 2697-2131, Vol.11. (156-161)

Mirzayev O. Formation of elements of entrepreneurial activity in pupils of the preschool educational organization. Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal - Journal NX/ISSN: 2581-4230/Impakt faktori: 7.2 (2020 -2021) Is Published Online in Volume-7, Issue-4, Apr. – 2021(265-267)

Mirzayev O. Methodological system for ensuring the international of elements of fairy-tale therapy and entrepreneurial culture. Web of synergy:international interdisciplinary research journal. Volume 2 issue 7, 2023 ISSN: 2835-3013(49-52)